

CLIMATE - RAPID EVALUATION FRAMEWORK

CMIP7 Quality Checklist

Terms and Conditions

Bibliographic Information

This report should be cited as: Hassler, B. Lewis, J., Lee, J., Andela, B., Swaminathan, R., Hoffman, F.M., Turner, B. and O'Rourke, E. (2026) Climate – Rapid Evaluation Framework QAQC CMIP7 Checklist (1.0), Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18915234>

Disclaimer

The designations employed in the WCRP Coupled Model Intercomparison Project, or CMIP, publications and the presentation of material in this publication do not imply the expression of any opinion whatsoever on the part of CMIP, the World Climate Research Programme (WCRP) – including its Sponsor Organizations the World Meteorological Organization (WMO), the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC) of UNESCO, and the International Science Council (ISC) – or the European Space Agency (ESA) in its role as host organisation of the CMIP International Project Office (CMIP-IPO), concerning the legal status of any country, territory, city or area or of its authorities, or concerning the delimitation of its frontiers or boundaries.

The findings, interpretations and conclusions expressed in CMIP publications with named authors are those of the authors alone and do not necessarily reflect those of CMIP, WCRP, its Sponsor Organizations, ESA or of their Members.

This document is not an official publication of the WCRP and has been issued without formal editing.

The views expressed herein do not necessarily have the endorsement of WCRP or its Members.

Any potential mention of specific companies or products does not imply that they are endorsed or recommended in preference to others of a similar nature which are not mentioned or advertised.

Copyright notice

This report is published by the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP) under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0, <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and thereunder made available for reuse for any purpose, subject to the license's terms, including proper attribution.

CMIP-IPO@esa.int

CMIP International Project Office
ESA ECSAT
Fermi Avenue
Harwell Campus
Didcot, Oxfordshire
OX11 0FD, United Kingdom

Authorship and publisher's notice

This report was authored by: Birgit Hassler, Jared Lewis, Jiwoo Lee, Bouwe Andela, Ranjini Swaminathan, Forrest M. Hoffman, Briony Turner and Eleanor O'Rourke

Acknowledgments

This document was prepared by members of the CMIP Model Benchmarking Task Team and the REF delivery team. This document has been reviewed by the governing panels of CMIP: CMIP Panel and the WCRP ESMO Infrastructure Panel (WIP).

The Rapid Evaluation Framework (REF) is a community project developed by CMIP, a project of ESMO, which is a core project of the World Climate Research Programme (WCRP). Development of the CMIP7 ready REF has been funded by :

U.S. DEPARTMENT
of ENERGY

REF Delivery partners:

RAL Space

Model evaluation packages within the REF

Contents

Terms and Conditions	2
1 Introduction	5
1.1 Quality Control for CMIP7	6
1.2 Learning from CMIP6.....	7
1.3 Impact of data not meeting the REF quality checklist	8
1.4 Treatment of data not passing the REF quality checklist	8
2 Quality Checks to integrate into workflow	9
2.1 Fillvalues	9
2.2 Attributes	9
2.3 Values	9
2.4 Branch information.....	9
2.5 Consistency	10
3 IOOS Quality Checks	11
3.1 Deploying the REF TOML file	11
3.2 Version control of the REF TOML file	11
3.3 CMIP7 IOOS compliance checker checks important for the REF	11
3.4 Checks for the REF in excess of required CMIP7 checks	11
Annex 1 Summary of the REF Required Quality Checks in excess of those required for CMIP7	12

1 Introduction

The Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP) is an international climate modelling project, designed to better understand past, present and future changes in Earth's climate. CMIP has been organized in different phases, each with new and improved climate model experiment protocols, standards, and data distribution mechanisms. Since CMIP6, the community has aimed to evaluate the simulations published on the Earth System Grid Federation¹ (ESGF) rapidly, providing near-real-time assessment to users.

The model evaluation ambition within the sixth phase of CMIP was to rapidly and routinely evaluate output as the simulations were published to ESGF and became available online. In CMIP6 this ambition was not met. A planned, quasi-operational evaluation framework could not be deployed due to complexities associated with the data quality of the submitted simulations. Deviations from the pre-defined, strict structure of file format and metadata information, even apparently minor ones, meant that implementation of fully automated and rapid evaluation directly after data publication was not possible for CMIP6 (Hassler, Hoffman et al., 2026). Any framework aimed at automated processing of input data would similarly fail unless stricter checks for data quality and metadata availability are adhered to by the modelling community.

During set up of the latest phase of CMIP, CMIP7, the scientific governing panel, the CMIP panel, established a dedicated task team, the Model Benchmarking Task Team, with a number of objectives which included developing a framework that allows quick simulation access and evaluation. The task team has since developed and implemented the Climate - Rapid Evaluation Framework (REF)² which is a community owned evaluation framework, built upon, and compatible with, existing community evaluation packages that incorporates an application programming interface (API) for executing metrics generated from community evaluation packages, across the globe. Three community evaluation and benchmarking packages are included in the Assessment Fast Track REF (ESMValTool, ILAMB-IOMB, PMP), each with their own data quality requirements. To make the REF fully functional, the requirements of all three packages must be met.

Building on the progress and lessons learned from previous CMIP phases, the CMIP Panel and community were strongly motivated to support and facilitate the use of CMIP7 data to address the CMIP7 research questions and deliver to scientific and wider user community e.g., , international assessment including IPCC, downstream activities and climate services (Dunne et al., 2025). With regard to this, and the requirements of the community packages in the REF, the CMIP Panel authorised the Model Benchmarking Task Team to proceed with developing the REF, stipulating that the REF would not be required to evaluate simulations that fail to meet required data-quality standards; if simulations cannot be processed by the REF, these simulations will be flagged or excluded from the public dashboard (see section 1.4).

Decision ID 49 (v): *If the submitted simulations are not correctly formatted, the REF will not work properly. In the event that the quality assurance (QA)/quality control (QC) cannot be*

¹ ESGF is a partnership of climate modelling centres dedicated to supporting climate research by providing secure, web-based, distributed access to climate model data, find out more here: <https://esgf.github.io/nodes.html>

² Find out more about the REF here: <https://climate-ref.org/>

enforced in the necessary strict way, the REF will provide evaluations/benchmarks for the correctly formatted simulations and exclude any that are not correctly formatted.

The REF leverages the attributes provided by datasets to automate the diagnostic generation process. This automation requires standardisation and coherent attributes across models, variables and experiments in order to correctly combine different datasets without manual selection by humans. These quality checks are, in some cases, in addition to the checks required for data publication to ESGF. They will improve the robustness of these published simulations, help reduce the errors raised when the REF is executed, and will improve published CMIP data quality for all, reducing the dependency of users on the use of errata³ for robust analysis by solving data quality issues prior to publication.

The REF is run both on ESGF, providing open access, and in a containerised version. Data that has been prepared to adhere to these quality checks ensures it is ready for REF ingestion. This effort at the data preparation stage by the modelling centres will help eliminate unnecessary data runs and use of scarce community compute for the publicly accessible REF as well as reducing the carbon footprint.

The quality checks set out in this document will enable use of the modelling centres' CMIP7 data in future REF diagnostics, not just the Assessment Fast Track. They are classified as 'high severity' checks. Modelling centres whose CMIP7 Fast Track simulations meet these requirements will maximise the likelihood of their outputs being included in the REF diagnostics. As the REF is an evolving, community tool, it is able to respond to the needs of, and provide benefit to, the wider environmental science community, therefore, model simulations successfully integrated with the REF will have broader reach across the scientific community.

1.1 Quality Control for CMIP7

The Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF) will facilitate the global distribution of CMIP7 output.

ESGF has a Quality Control (QC) solution based on a plugin developed for the IOOS Compliance Checker: <https://ioos.github.io/compliance-checker/>. It provides a mechanism to validate climate model outputs intended for publication on ESGF. The goal of this plugin is to provide a cohesive, extensible, and transparent system that consolidates key checks for WCRP projects, covers at least the minimum requirements for ESGF publication, and produces standardized reporting. In CMIP7 the IOOS Compliance Checker is used for QC but is also available to modelling centres to run before publication in their own quality assurance processes to check data compliance, see: https://wcrp-cmip.github.io/cmip7-guidance/docs/CMIP7/Guidance_for_modellers/#7-software-for-checking-output. The IOOS Compliance Checker checks can be applied by modelling centres before publication and are integrated into the ESGF publication configuration. The majority of quality checks the REF requires need to be deployed pre-publication and are reliant on modelling centres integrating these checks into their data preparation workflows.

For CMIP7 the WCRP ESMO Infrastructure Panel (WIP) has approved a required set of severity Quality Control checks ranging from high to low which must be passed in order to publish to ESGF.

³ The ESGF Errata platform offers issue tracking services for known issues in ESGF datasets. It also provides documentation on data version changes. Find out more about CMIP errata here: https://wcrp-cmip.org/cmip-data-access/#errata_and_known_issues_with_datasets

The Rapid Evaluation Framework requires a number of additional pre-publication **quality checks** for successful ingest and use of CMIP7 data. This document sets out the case for modelling centres to deploy the REF's quality checks in excess of, as well as, those required for CMIP7 data publication. A full list of the additional quality checks can be found in Annex 1.

1.2 Learning from CMIP6

Model benchmarking can be seen as a stress-test on the QA/QC processes as diagnostics frequently combine results from multiple models, experiments and variables. This cross-dataset analysis requires consistency in data standardisation and any differences between modelling centres become apparent through either incorrect results, or having to fix/exclude datasets.

Broadly, in CMIP6 any issues with the key attributes that were included in the files were often identified and remedied via the errata process, but other more subtle errors were left unidentified or uncorrected with implications for model evaluation and benchmarking. The CMIP Model Benchmarking Task Team wish to highlight the following errors:

- Incorrect branch information, making it difficult to automate stitching together experiments
 - Branch times not matching parent experiments
 - Parent identifiers referencing incorrect or missing simulation ensemble members
- Errors in units requiring scaling of results
- Incorrect reporting of coordinate and bounds values
- Parametric vertical coordinates not conforming to CF Convention requirements or CMIP output requirements
- Errors in the fillvalue, resulting in incorrect masking/interpretation of the data
- Differently rounded coordinate values within a dataset, impairing concatenation of dataset files
- Differences in reporting ancillary variables
- Missing scalar height coordinates
- Extra attributes in unexpected places, such as a “history” attribute on a coordinate variable, that make the datasets more heterogeneous and processing difficult to automate

Some of these may not have been inconsistent with the CMIP6 global attribute definitions or data request but were identified as sources of inconsistency in how different models interpreted the definitions. In several cases, issues were clearly introduced due to manual modifications to the files after the automatic preparation process was finished.

Downstream consumers of CMIP6 data often implemented fixes to datasets as they were found. The CMIP6 fixes implemented by ESMValTool can be found here: https://github.com/ESMValGroup/ESMValCore/tree/843be03dcdb286c8a8b092f29575994cc58c59aa/esmvalcore/cmor/_fixes/cmip6. We recommend modelling centres review the fixes made to their CMIP6 datasets before publication of CMIP7. These fixes were often bespoke to the type of analysis being performed with no single source of truth. This required significant duplication of effort across the community. This also increases the required complexity of all downstream consumers due to the requirement to handle different edge cases.

The CMIP7 QC process aims to mitigate most of these by performing checks at publication time (see section 1.1).

1.3 Impact of data not meeting the REF quality checklist

Without the checks specified in this document:

- files might be unreadable or misinterpreted by REF software and might not be usable for the intended diagnostics.
- files might not be able to be concatenated automatically by REF software and will not be included in REF analyses.
- data read and analysed by the REF might produce incorrect metrics and diagnostics (e.g. plots would look wrong).

1.4 Treatment of data not passing the REF quality checklist

The REF will attempt to ingest datasets that may not comply with the additional checks outlined in this document. The REF does not perform additional checks at ingest time other than parsing of basic metadata covered by the required CMIP7 QC checks (see section 1.1). Non-compliance may cause incorrect datasets to be selected for a given execution, or the diagnostic calculation to fail. This may result in the presentation of failing executions in the portal, or worse produce scientifically invalid results. To mitigate this the REF will:

- distribute a “greylist⁴” of files that will be excluded from specific diagnostics
- include basic outlier detection to exclude potentially invalid metrics by default
- recalculate affected diagnostics if a new version of a dataset is published

The REF will not itself attempt to implement fixes for incompatible datasets but would adopt a community-maintained set of fixes if that is developed. Corrections of errors would likely require updates to the diagnostic codes contributed to the REF, causing significant delays in the analysis of the incompatible datasets.

In the following sections, for each quality check in the summary table in Annex 1, the REF Impact level is identified as:

- **High:** REF will not run
- **Medium:** REF will run but with major impact (e.g., large error in the result)
- **Low:** REF will run with minor impact (e.g., subtle difference in the result, figure may have incorrect caption, etc.)

⁴ The criteria for inclusion on the greylist and management of notification of inclusion communications to modelling centres, likely via the Errata system, will be formalised by the incoming ESMO REF governance panel. At time of issue the current greylist is available here: https://github.com/Climate-REF/climate-ref/blob/main/default_ignore_datasets.yaml

2 Quality Checks to integrate into workflow

The underlying IOOS framework on which ESGF Quality Control solution is built operates primarily at the file level and therefore applies checks that are independent across files. A number of these the checks required for functioning of the REF are beyond the technical limits of what the current framework can reasonably support.

Modelling centres are encouraged to integrate into their workflows a review of output for adherence to the quality checks set out in this section, prior to publication. If any of these checks become integrated into the IOOS framework, this document will be updated and a new version released.

A number of these quality check requirements relate to the Global attributes - for more information on this see: Global attributes doc at [CMIP7 Global Attributes, DRS, Filenames, Directory Structure, and CVs](#).

2.1 Fillvalues

- **FillValue or missing_value attribute dtype does not match data dtype** (- this could lead to wrongly interpreting the data and therefore producing misleading plots and other results. The modelling centres are reminded that the WIP require that for all float32 data, the FillValue(s) and missing_value(s), must be 1.0e20 (not just any float32 number).
- **Data uses a different _FillValue/missing_value than declared in the attribute** - this could lead to wrongly interpreting the data and therefore producing misleading plots and other results

2.2 Attributes

- **Incorrect value for parent_time_units attribute** - is important for diagnostics that require more information from simulations other than the historical simulation (e.g. ECS, TCR, TCRE, ZEC)
- **Units attribute does not correspond to the actual data** (e.g. data in degrees Celsius but units say Kelvin, data is a fraction but units say percentage) - this could lead to wrongly interpreting the data and therefore producing misleading plots and other results
- **Differences in long_name for horizontal index coordinates for 2D grids within the same dataset** (no need to read the data) - problems to concatenate files to cover the whole to-be-analysed period

2.3 Values

- **Data uses opposite sign than defined direction** (e.g., eastward surface wind stress (tauu), upward/downward radiation flux) - this could lead to wrongly interpreting the data and therefore producing misleading plots and other results
- **Slightly different coordinate and bounds values within the same dataset** (e.g. some of the files may contain values that have been rounded to a lower precision) (need to read the data) - problems to concatenate files to cover the whole to-be-analysed period

2.4 Branch information

- **Check that the `branch_time` in `parent_variant_label` of different experiments corresponds to `variant_label` from the parent experiment (`variant_label`)** - is necessary to be able to calculate diagnostics that require more information from simulations other than the historical simulation (e.g. ECS, TCR, TCRE, ZEC)
- **Check the `branch_time_in_parent` of different experiments reflects continuity from the parent experiment (`branch_time_in_parent`)** - is necessary to be able to calculate diagnostics that require more information from simulations other than the historical simulation (e.g. ECS, TCR, TCRE, ZEC)
- **`branch_time`, `branch_time_in_parent`, `branch_time_in_child`** (existence, correct type, etc.) - is necessary to be able to calculate diagnostics that require more information from simulations other than the historical simulation (e.g. ECS, TCR, TCRE, ZEC)

Please note that `branch_method`, was previously important for the packages within the REF but has been dropped from the Global Attributes for CMIP7

2.5 Consistency

- **Check the consistency across all files from the same dataset (time period)** - important for being able to concatenate files to span the full time period to be analysed

2.6 Long_Name

- **Wrong or missing `long_name`** - whilst there is no officially standardized definition of `long_name`, one of the packages, ESMValTool, requires that the `long_name` from the CMOR tables is used.
- **The `long_name`** will be validated at medium priority by the CMIP7 quality check, i.e. it will not prevent publication if this differs from the expected value. Following the introduction of Branded Variables and the restructuring in preparation for the Variable Registry there are a small set of variables where the long name has to be overridden by the data provider to match the Data Request.

3 IOOS Quality Checks

3.1 Deploying the REF TOML file

The mandatory CMIP7 checks will be routinely imposed as part of the publication job stream, but the REF checks need to be executed by a modelling group prior to publication. If a dataset raises no errors when checked by the REF-configured, combined with CMIP7-configured IOOS compliance checker, then the dataset will be publishable as well as being acceptable for REF analysis.

Whilst currently there are no additional checks within the IOOS compliance checker for the REF to those mandatory for CMIP7, preparation has been made for future iterations, where the REF might have a separate toml file with additional checks as they become available. This will be linked to, with appropriate guidance, from the [REF guidance on GitHub](#).

3.2 Version control of the REF TOML file

The IOOS compliance checker will be further developed. In time, some of the current additional quality checks for the REF might become available as quality control checks in the IOOS QC solution. In that situation the REF toml file will be updated alongside this document and new versions of both released.

3.3 CMIP7 IOOS compliance checker checks important for the REF

The following checks within the CMIP7 IOOS compliance checker are particularly important for the REF:

3.3.1 Auxiliary information

- **ensuring areacella, areacello and volcello files are in place for every simulation** – without this information many diagnostics (especially area or volume aggregated calculations) cannot perform correctly.

3.3.3 Consistency

- **Check the consistency across all files from the same dataset** (nominal_resolution, project-related attributes) – important for being able to concatenate files to span the full period to be analysed

3.4 Checks for the REF in excess of required CMIP7 checks

The REF requires higher severity for the following checks:

cmip7_output_requirements.calendar (Annex 1, ID15) – it is important for one of the packages within the REF that the calendar is correct and that it is the same for all files within a dataset and the same across datasets that we concatenate or otherwise compare, e.g. the historical and a scenario experiment for the global warming levels diagnostic or a child and parent experiment for computing ZEC, TCR, TCRE, and ECS.

We anticipate this will be integrated into the CMIP7 QC checks in the future, subject to approval by the WIP.

Annex 1 Summary of the REF Required Quality Checks in excess of those required for CMIP7

This table is ordered and shaded according to the impact non-compliance of the check would have on the REF.

ID	Description	Impact level	Reason for exclusion from ESGF QC solution
2	Wrong or missing long_name attribute for coordinate	High - REF will not run	There is no officially standardized definition of long_name
7	ensuring areacella and areacello files are in place	High - REF will not run	Not yet implemented
16	Differences in long_name for horizontal index coordinates for 2D grids within the same dataset (no need to read the data)	High - REF will not run	non-applicable (or challenging to automatize)
17	Slightly different coordinate and bounds values within the same dataset (need to read the data)	High - REF will not run	Not yet implemented
19	Branch_method, branch_time, branch_time_in_parent, branch_time_in_child (existence, correct type, etc.)	High - REF will not run	non-applicable (or challenging to automatize)
5	FillValue or missing_value attribute dtype does not match data dtype (for example: data dtype is float32 and missing value dtype is float64)	Medium - REF will run but with major impact	Not yet implemented
12	Units attribute does not correspond to the actual data (e.g. data in degrees Celsius but units say Kelvin, data is a fraction but units say percentage)	Medium - REF will run but with major impact	Not yet implemented
13	Data uses a different _FillValue/missing_value than declared in the attribute	Medium - REF will run but with major impact	Not yet implemented
14	Data uses opposite sign then defined direction (e.g., eastward surface wind stress (tauu), upward/downward radiation flux)	Medium - REF will run but with major impact	Non-applicable (or challenging to automatize)
22	Check the parent_variant_label of different experiments corresponds to variant_label from the parent experiment (variant_label)	Medium - REF will run but with major impact	Non-applicable (or challenging to automatize)
23	Check the branch_time_in_parent of different experiments reflects continuity from the parent experiment (branch_time_in_parent)	Medium - REF will run but with major impact	Not yet implemented
24	Check the consistency across all files from the same dataset (nominal_resolution)	Medium - REF will run but with major impact	Non-applicable (or challenging to automatize)
26	Check the consistency across all files from the same dataset time period)	Medium - REF will run but with major impact	Non-applicable (or challenging to automatize)
28	Check the consistency across all files from the same dataset (project-related global attributes)	Medium - REF will run but with major impact	Non-applicable (or challenging to automatize)
3	Invalid value for parent_time_units attribute	Low - REF will run with minor impact	Non-applicable (or challenging to automatize)